

Equity, Diversity, & Inclusion Committee

Report 2025

(Prepared for CGU Executive & Membership)

Dave, Riddhi¹ & Leclerc, Natasha²

¹Natural Resources Canada, ²Memorial University of Newfoundland

¹riddhi.dave@nrcan-rncan.gc.ca, ²ndhlnl2@mun.ca

Committee email: edi@cgu-ugc.ca

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Contents

- 1 Historical Background 2
- 2 Mission Statement 2
- 3 Summary of Goals 3
- 4 Report Objectives 3
- 5 Committee Highlights (2021 - 2024) 3
- 6 Overview of Activities (2023 - 2024) 4
- 7 Key Initiatives and Outcomes 5
- 8 Goals for 2025 7
- 9 Short-Term Vision (2–3 Years) 7
- 10 Survey Statistics 8
- 11 EDI Survey Summary 12
- 12 Acknowledgements 17
- 13 How To Cite 17

1. Historical Background

Following the example of other professional societies (i.e., AGG, AGU, EGU and others), the Canadian Geophysical Union - Equity, Diversity, and Inclusion (CGU-EDI) committee was first established in 2018 by two section executives: Jacklyn Cockburn (University of Guelph) and Claire Oswald (Toronto Metropolitan University). Early initiatives included formalizing a code of conduct for the conference and developing a survey (2021). Near the time of the committee's formation, an article was published in FACETS, which included a diversity survey from the 2017 CGU conference (King et al., 2018). These early data have been compiled and included in our statistical analysis of EDI trends covering 4 years (2017, 2021, 2023, and 2024).

2. Mission Statement

The CGU is committed to fostering an inclusive, equitable, and welcoming environment for all geoscientists to share their research and ideas. Since its establishment, the EDI committee has strived to address the well-established and ongoing systemic challenges in the geosciences. Guided by the core values of respect, accessibility, and accountability, our mission is to build a community that actively promotes and implements best practices in equity, diversity, and inclusion. Through the organization of EDI-focused events, management of annual meeting registration waivers, and continual assessment via member feedback, we aim to create lasting, structural changes that better serve our members and enrich the field of geoscience. By supporting these efforts, we are dedicated to ensuring that the CGU remains a place where all contributions are valued and all members can thrive.

3. Summary of Goals

- Attract and retain a diverse community of researchers across the Canadian geoscience landscape
- Promote inclusive dialogue by offering both in-person and virtual spaces to discuss EDI-focused issues and initiatives while addressing systemic challenges within the discipline
- Standardize data collection to enable consistent, long-term tracking and analysis of equity, diversity, and inclusion within the CGU
- Foster a vibrant, welcoming, and active committee where every voice is heard and valued, encouraging new members to engage and contribute diverse perspectives

4. Report Objectives

This report presents an overview of our annual activities along with strategic plans for the coming year. Additionally, we share findings from the annual EDI Survey, including data and trend analysis compared to previous years. As the first summative report of its kind for the CGU, we aim for this document to serve as a foundational template and establish benchmarks for future assessments.

5. Committee Highlights (2021 - 2024)

- Administered registration fee waivers to enhance accessibility and support broader participation at CGU 2024
- Successfully organized well-attended and well-received EDI plenaries in both 2023 and 2024, as well as the first-ever EDI-focused technical session in CGU history in 2024
- Published this report outlining the committee's historical context, mission, vision for

the future, and survey statistics spanning 2017 to 2024

- Witnessed sustained and growing engagement in committee activities, reflected in increased participation and enthusiastic turnout at events

6. Overview of Activities (2023 - 2024)

The following infographic illustrates the feedback received during the EDI sessions at CGU 2023 and the corresponding implementations made in the subsequent year. Efforts are ongoing to further address the feedback and continue tackling EDI-related issues.

Figure 1: Feedback on EDI sessions at the CGU Annual Meeting, May 2023

7. Key Initiatives and Outcomes

- **Regular meetings:** The committee held seven meetings throughout the year to discuss and strategize EDI initiatives within CGU activities
- **Registration Fee Waivers (RFW):** Six CGU conference RFWs were provided to individuals from underrepresented groups to support their attendance at the annual meeting
- **EDI-related accommodations:** A comprehensive list of accommodations was developed to support a welcoming and inclusive environment. These include a welcoming mixer for BIPOC, women, and LGBTQ+ attendees; quiet spaces; a prayer room; childcare facilities; breastfeeding rooms; mobility considerations (e.g., accessible stages); and EDI posters celebrating diversity within the CGU
- **By-laws amendment:** The committee is currently updating the by-laws to incorporate stronger equity, diversity, and inclusion (EDI) policies and practices, with completion planned ahead of CGU 2025
- **Integrated EDI survey in registration:** The EDI survey was included in the CGU conference registration to gather feedback and demographic data on participants' needs and experiences, which (along with previous year's surveys) was used to inform the writing of this report
- **EDI handouts:** A handout guide was developed and distributed for CGU session organizers with best practices for fostering diverse, inclusive, and accessible sessions
- **EDI plenary at CGU:** Organized a well-attended plenary session featuring two speakers (Minoli Dias and Lindsay Schoenbohm) exploring the experiences of minority undergraduate students in geosciences and insights from a demographic survey of Canadian geoscience academia. *See the infographic chart below for more information*

- **Inaugural EDI technical session at CGU:** Co-organized a technical session on *Hidden Figures in the Geosciences* with colleagues from the University of Northern British Columbia and McMaster University. The session featured four talks on themes such as colonial legacies, community vs. academia, conference practices, and representation statistics in geosciences, followed by a roundtable discussion. *See the infographic chart below for more information*
- **Integration of EDI committee in awards adjudication:** An EDI committee member is now included in the adjudication process of union-level awards
- **CGU-EDI Report:** Published a detailed report on the historical background, mission statement, future vision, and survey statistics (2017 - 2024)

Figure 2: Attendee characterization from CGU-EDI sessions 2024

8. Goals for 2025

- Promote and advertise the CGU Annual General Meeting (AGM) to a wider audience (e.g., online-based science-communication workshop and social media presence)
- Establish clear criteria for the adjudication of registration waivers
- Develop guidelines for integrating new EDI committee members into the by-laws
- Integrate an EDI-focused survey into the membership renewal process
- Enhance transparency by publishing committee documents and survey results to identify actionable trends and areas for growth (e.g., website development)
- Increase visibility and engagement with CGU-EDI issues and activities (i.e., website with contact links)

9. Short-Term Vision (2–3 Years)

- **Enhance Accessibility at Conferences:** Provide dedicated accommodation spaces at CGU conferences to support a range of attendee needs, including childcare services, prayer rooms, breastfeeding spaces, and quiet rooms
- **Expand and Strengthen Committee Membership:** Proactively attract new committee members who align with and aim to exceed the EDI principles embedded in the committee's mission and by-laws
- **Increase Member Engagement and Action-Oriented Dialogue:** Strengthen member participation in EDI initiatives by fostering community-informed discussion during the Annual Business Meeting (ABM), leading to actionable outcomes and collaborative planning
- **Foster Intersectional Collaboration:** Host a joint event between CGU-EDI and Women Geoscientists in Canada (WGC), with a focus on intersectionality, knowledge-sharing, and expanding the impact and reach of EDI efforts across the geoscience

community

10. Survey Statistics

Figure 3: Male-presenting, female-presenting, and presenters of color from observed sessions from (King et al., 2018). King et al. (2018) analyzed data from the joint Canadian Geophysical Union and Canadian Society of Agricultural and Forest Meteorology annual meeting (CGU-CSAFM 2017), examining participation, presentation content, and behaviour in conference sessions. The graph above depicts male-presenting, female-presenting presenters, and presenters of colour from observed sessions. These numbers are based solely on visual identification from the sessions monitored.

Figure 4: Data from the 2024 CGU-EDI survey illustrates the career stages and gender identities of respondents. The Y-axis represents percentages, while the values inside the bars indicate the total number of respondents for each gender.

Figure 5: Dynamic racing graphs of Gender Identity, Indigeneity, LGBTQTS+, and Racial Minority with y-axis items evolving over 2021, 2023, and 2024, providing a clear visualization of leaders and laggards, allowing for the comparison of relative performance.

Figure 6: Dynamic racing graphs of Disability, CGU attendance, Section Affiliation, Career Stage, and Duration in Current Role, with y-axis items evolving over 2021, 2023, and 2024, providing a clear visualization of leaders and laggards, allowing for the comparison of relative performance.

11. EDI Survey Summary

- Figure 4 bar chart highlights a classic 'Leaky Pipeline' trend, with minority representation declining at advanced career stages (10–25 years). Data for later career stages (>25 years) is less reliable due to the low number of respondents, likely influenced by the nature of the conference and the survey's primary audience—students and early career researchers
- Figures 5 and 6 survey participation shows a notable change in respondent engagement from 2023 to 2024. In 2023, responses on diversity-related topics dropped significantly, with the number of participants falling from 290 to 135. However, in 2024, there was an improvement in respondents' willingness to answer EDI-related questions, with participation levels stabilizing. Unfortunately, we do not have sufficient data to make comparisons with the 2021 survey
- It is also worth noting that no survey was conducted in 2022 (Figures 5 and 6)
- Looking ahead, addressing inconsistencies in question formatting and answer options will be crucial to enhance the clarity and relevance of the survey
- Additionally, including questions on higher levels of education (such as MSc, PhD, and professional degrees) would help assess representation across various academic stages, particularly at the faculty level
- Analyzing survey statistics from various reports (e.g., Smith et al. (2023)) provides valuable insights into the current state of Equity, Diversity, and Inclusion (EDI) within Canadian geoscience academia and can be an important item on the agenda for future CGU EDI reports

Our Members

Philip Heron - Chair

Phil is an Assistant Professor in Environmental Geophysics at the University of Toronto (Scarborough Campus). He conducts geoscience research on plate tectonic processes and also works in the field of science communication – publishing research around accessible and inclusive science practices. Phil also runs the outreach program called Think Like A Scientist, which works predominantly in improving access to education for marginalized groups, including people in English, Canadian, and Australian prisons.

Natasha Leclerc - Co-Chair

Natasha is an Adjunct Professor and Postdoctoral Fellow in Archaeology at Memorial University of Newfoundland. She is an interdisciplinary researcher connecting paleoenvironmental data from the geochemical analysis of biogenic calcifiers to Indigenous-led concerns and questions. Her current work aims to support community involvement throughout the research process, including the co-development of mutually beneficial objectives and research dissemination.

Riddhi Dave

Riddhi is a Research Scientist at Natural Resources Canada and an Adjunct Professor at the University of British Columbia, based in Vancouver. She specializes in the multidisciplinary mapping of lithospheric architecture with applications in critical mineral prospectivity, glacio-isostatic adjustment modeling, seismic hazards, and more. Passionate about outreach and EDI efforts, she is actively involved in grassroots initiatives aimed at amplifying the voices of diverse and marginalized groups across government, academia, and industry.

Kelly Biagi

Kelly is an Assistant Professor in Earth Science at Brock University. Her research focuses on landscape hydrology and restoration with a focus on wetlands. Kelly is passionate about increasing diversity, inclusion and accessibility in STEM and wants to help address the 'leaky pipeline' issue in academia, which she has witnessed first-hand.

Colin McCarter

Colin is a Canada Research Chair and Assistant Professor in Biology, Chemistry and Geography at Nipissing University. Stemming from his own experiences with his neurodiversity in academia, he provides mentorship to neurodiverse students and shares his own adaptive strategies. He encourages anyone to reach out to him if they are interested in neurodiversity in academia. As he has become more aware of other inequities and biases in academia, he has sought opportunities to learn more and engage in wider conversations about EDI. Colin joined the committee in 2021 to better promote a more equitable, diverse, and inclusive atmosphere in Canadian geosciences.

Mohammad Fereshtehpour

Mohammad is a Research Associate in hydrotechnical engineering at York University, focusing on climate change adaptation and flood risk analysis. His work explores innovative ways to model inland and coastal flooding, with a goal of developing sustainable solutions for communities facing increasing hydroclimatic hazards. Driven by a steadfast belief that diversity and inclusion ignite transformative innovation, he joined the EDI committee to advocate for research cultures where bold ideas flourish. His mission is to ensure climate adaptation strategies are co-created with equity at their core, empowering every community—especially those most vulnerable—to thrive in a changing world.

Adeyemi Olusola

Adeyemi is an Assistant Professor at the Faculty of Environmental and Urban Change at York University. He is a physical geographer interested in rivers and their processes across scales (from the reach to the continental scale). His overarching research focus is understanding the dynamics and drivers of river processes and their implications on river corridors. As against the concept of looking at rivers as a mere conveyor of water, he considers rivers as corridors, that is, spaces of interaction. As a Black scholar of African descent, he is deeply committed to advancing EDI practices within and outside my immediate academic environment. He joined the EDI committee because its values and mandate fall within his priority as a geoscientist.

12. Acknowledgements

Warm thanks to Jaclyn Cockburn (University of Guelph), Claire Oswald (Toronto Metropolitan University), Carl Mitchell (UTSC) and Julian Lowman (UTSC) for providing historical background information on the establishment of the EDI Committee.

13. How To Cite

Dave, R., & Leclerc, N. (2025). *Canadian Geophysical Union - Equity, Diversity, & Inclusion Committee Report 2025*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15237908>

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